

SUPER PV PROJECT INNOVATIONS - LCOE ASSESSMENT AND COMPETITIVENESS

Torstein Haarberg¹, Philippe Macé², Elina Bosch², Juras Ulbikas³, Julius Denafas⁴, Alexander Ulyashin⁵

¹BNW-Energy AS, Trondheim, 7048, Norway, th@bnw-energy.com; ²Becquerel Institute, Brussels, 1000, Belgium; ³Applied Research Institute for Prospective Technologies (Protech), Vilnius, LT 10243, Lithuania; ⁴SOLITEK R&D, Vilnius, 08412, Lithuania; ⁵SINTEF Industry, Oslo, 0134, Norway

ABSTRACT: The performance of innovations in the ongoing Horizon 2020 project SUPER PV are assessed, both for individual innovations and at an integral level, by calculating the LCOE as the key performance variable. New prospective innovations from SUPER PV combined with price reductions and improvements elsewhere in the PV supply chain are evaluated. Such hybrid solutions can form winning combinations in the market and may point towards a flexible business model for non-vertically integrated module manufacturers.

Several SUPER PV innovations show clear commercial potential by comparing the LCOE with and without the innovation. Moreover, the "*SUPER PV best estimate*", i.e., the combination of SUPER PV innovations and cost reductions in segments of the PV supply chain not covered by the project, leads to a total estimated LCOE reduction of 57% compared with the original benchmark at the start of the project, considerably lower than the originally targeted 37% LCOE reduction.

At this point the results from SUPER PV are overall promising. Key activities forward are validation of results at the SUPER PV demo-sites across Europe and North Africa and to prepare business models and -plans for market uptake after project end (October 2022).

Keywords: Economic Analysis, LCOE, Markets, PV System Performance

1 INTRODUCTION

The SUPER PV project started in 2018 with 26 partners from 11 countries across Europe and North Africa and targets a range of innovations at three main segments within the PV value chain: PV module innovations, power electronics enhancements and new system integration approaches, including software for design and operation of PV facilities.

The timing of SUPER PV has proven to be perfect, as key issues addressed in the project has become among the most discussed and trending topics in the solar PV community in recent years, from digitalisation of the PV sector and big data analytics, through progress in manufacturing of advanced PV modules and the introduction of bifacial solar modules, to new approaches for solar module recycling.

A common denominator for many SUPER PV innovations is enhanced energy yield. Moreover, unlike a project where solar cells are being developed as a main objective, cheaper and better solar cells in the market will add to the competitiveness of SUPER PV-based solutions. The same goes for other innovations and improvements in the solar supply chain not covered by the project.

2 SCOPE AND APPROACH

2.1 Scope

The scope of this work is to assess the performance of innovations developed in the ongoing project SUPER PV by means of Levelised Cost of Energy (LCOE) assessment as the central Key Performance Indicator (KPI), both at an individual- and an integral level. In addition to the LCOE also other KPIs were identified already from the start of the project:

- Solar module cost reduction
- BoS components costs (EUR/Wp)
- Total installation cost (EUR/Wp)

- Performance Ratio (PR) over the lifetime
- Recyclability and environmental footprint of solar modules.

The general methodology is explained below and illustrated with concrete examples in the results section.

2.2 Approach and methodology

LCOE can be thought of as the price at which electricity must be sold to the market to break even over the lifetime of the technology. It represents the present value of lifecycle cost divided by the present value of total electric power generation, in terms of, for example, €-cents per kilowatt-hour:

$$LCOE = \frac{\text{Present value of lifecycle cost}}{\text{Present value of lifetime energy production}}$$

The basic approach in this work is to study the effect on the LCOE by introducing changes to a PV system from new potential innovations. Individual performance assessments are done by evaluating the impact of a given innovation on the LCOE from added costs (e.g., component cost) and benefits (e.g., enhanced energy yield). If the calculated LCOE is reduced by adding an innovation, the innovation is deemed profitable, and vice versa. For most innovations this is a straightforward calculation, while for some innovations the situation is more complex. The performance of multifunctional nano-coatings is a good example of this complexity, as the integral effect of coatings requires knowledge on several variables, including coating cost and durability, changes on cleaning costs and, finally, impact on the energy yield and PR.

Integral performance assessments are done by calculating the total change in the LCOE from the combined set of innovations.

Supplemental KPIs described above are monitored continuously to achieve a best possible overview of the

technical progression of the project.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Performance of individual innovations

SUPER PV innovations cover three main segments within the PV value chain: PV module innovations, power electronics enhancements and new system integration approaches, including software for design and operation of PV facilities. Prospective innovations in SUPER PV that are subject to performance assessment are: Module front-sheet multifunctional nano-coatings, Light harvesting bifacial modules, In-laminate bypass diode, CIGS modules TPO/AlxOy barrier, PV module recycling, GaN based micro-inverter, MLPE (module level power electronics) micro-inverter, MLPE smartbox, Fault-tolerant converter, Data mining of manufacturing process, Cost-driven design and operation of PV plant software, O&M and smart monitoring with digital twin software, Bifacial modules enhanced yield with and without artificially enhanced ground albedo, Wireless communication gateways and IoT platforms, Weather monitoring, and Dust sensor.

While a thorough discussion of each individual innovation is beyond the scope of this paper, the approach and methodology are illustrated with concrete examples below. The integral effect of all prospective innovations is described in section 3.2.

Multifunctional nano-coatings will influence several defined KPIs. However, the quantitative effects from nano-coatings on the KPIs do not appear straightforward. The methodology for obtaining these relations is described below, using SUPER PV nano-coatings target values.

Target values for coating cost (€/m²) and durability (years) are first converted into a *present value* which represents all coating costs during the anticipated lifetime of the PV facility. For consistency and cost-comparison with commercial AR-coatings, the initial coating cost is not included in this calculation, as it is considered incorporated into the solar module cost. The calculated present value of all future coating replacements is converted into a corresponding (hypothetical) annual Operational and Maintenance (O&M) cost per Wp as shown in Figure 1. As illustrated in Figure 1 *coating economics* is more favourable at increasing electric power density (W/m²). This trivial mathematical result may nonetheless be quite interesting commercially.

Figure 1: Present value of annual coating O&M cost at varying coating replacement rate (yrs) and -cost (€/m²)

The overall effect of coatings should be a combination

of changes in O&M cost and PR. The effect on O&M has both a negative contribution as illustrated in Figure 1, and a positive contribution with less manual cleaning and maintenance. The integral effect of all impact factors from coatings is assessed by calculating the LCOE at varying O&M and PR, shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: LCOE change vs change in PR and O&M, multifunctional nano-coatings

The LCOE is calculated at a discount rate of 5% to enable direct comparison with evaluations in [1], and the situation is profitable for LCOE change <100%. The vertical, coloured lines in Figure 2 indicate the coating cost at 20% module efficiency, from Figure 1. Ongoing field tests at the SUPER PV demo-sites will be used in conjunction with the information in Figure 1 and 2 to give a final assessment of SUPER PV multifunctional nano-coatings.

MLPE Smartbox represents a new product, and there is hence no absolute benchmark for this innovation. The overall performance of the Smartbox is assessed as the relative change in LCOE at the targeted component cost of 0.03€/Wp for varying O&M and PR, as illustrated in Figure 3. An LCOE change <100% indicates profitability. Gains in O&M and PR are to be validated in the remaining part of the project.

Figure 3: LCOE change vs change in PR and O&M, MLPE Smartbox

Artificially enhanced albedo may enhance the energy yield for bifacial solar modules. Surface albedo has a big effect and is also considered the largest source of uncertainty for bifacial gain. A simplified calculation of yield gain vs albedo change is given in [2], indicating a yield gain of 5-7% by enhancing the surface albedo from 30% to 70%. A material with 70% initial albedo at a cost of approximately 0.5 €/ct/Wp is identified. The performance of this material is assessed coarsely, by asking: *How much extra operating*

costs can be allowed for such a material to be profitable?

Figure 4 shows the results of the assessment, based on an LCOE calculation vs extra O&M costs and enhanced yield, where the threshold line signifies the extra O&M cost at which the high albedo material breaks even. The material is assumed to be replaced after some years, at an overall installation / replacement cost twice the material cost, i.e., 1 €/ct/Wp (per replacement).

Figure 4: Estimated performance of high albedo material

Fixed costs at replacement by 3 and 5 years are plotted in the figure. It will be profitable to use the high albedo material when the total extra costs are below the blue threshold line.

3.2 Integral assessments

Three types of assessments are shown at the integral level (artificially enhanced albedo not included):

- 1) Comparison with the original benchmark set at the start of the SUPER PV project
- 2) Competitiveness in the PV market: Assessment vs defined reference cases that represent current and projected (2023) market conditions for large rooftop systems and ground mounted (utility-scale) systems, respectively
- 3) PV Performance in different geographies; LCOE vs long-term foreseen electricity prices in different countries in Europe and North Africa.

LCOE comparison with the original benchmark is shown in Figure 5. The original benchmark or *base case* constitutes the situation at project start, and initially a 37% LCOE reduction were targeted, as described in [3].

Figure 5: Calculated SUPER PV LCOE change, original and revised target

The revised target constitutes the "SUPER PV best estimate", i.e., the combination of SUPER PV innovations and cost reductions in segments of the PV supply chain not covered by the project such as cheaper solar cells and reduced Balance of System costs. This combination of project innovations and external innovations leads to a

total cost reduction of about 57%, as compared with the originally targeted 37%. This may point towards a flexible business model for non-vertically integrated module manufacturers which are able to capitalise on cost reductions not covered in-house.

Performance data for SUPER PV *best estimate* are shown in Table I. The targeted CAPEX cost is higher than recent system installation cost data from e.g., ITRPV [4]. This disadvantage for SUPER PV is however compensated by enhanced energy yield, giving an overall lower LCOE, as discussed below.

Table I: System performance, SUPER PV *best estimate*, ground-mounted system

Variable	Value	Unit
Installation cost, CAPEX	0.5525	€/Wp
Total OPEX	11	€/(kWp year)
Lifetime	35	year
Degradation rate	0.1	%/year
LID degradation 1 st year	2	%
Initial module efficiency	20	%
PR enhancement	7	%
Bifacial enhanced yield	7.5	%

Competitiveness in the PV market is shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7. The benchmark is constituted of commercially available technologies which have been identified as being representative of current (2021) and projected (2023) market and industry reality.

Figure 6: LCOE assessment of the SUPER PV best estimate vs defined benchmark for ground-mounted systems

Figure 7: LCOE assessment of the SUPER PV best estimate vs defined benchmark for large rooftop systems

Even though the system CAPEX reached with the SUPER PV innovations is higher than for the benchmark, the LCOE values obtained by the "SUPER PV best

estimate” are lower, both when looking at current and projected situation and at ground-mounted and large rooftop systems. This is made possible by higher yield reached by the “SUPER PV best estimate” system, thanks to significant gains in terms of Performance Ratio, which allows to harvest more solar energy at the same level of irradiance. The increased system lifetime (i.e., 35 years compared to 30 years for the benchmark) is a further explanation for these results. It should however be noted that the benchmark is constituted of monofacial modules, while the SUPER PV case assumes bifacial modules. Therefore, the Performance Ratio estimated to be reached by the SUPER PV case is heavily influenced by the bifaciality gains. Should the SUPER PV best estimate be compared to a benchmark based on bifacial modules for, it is likely that the advantage of the SUPER PV case would be substantially reduced, even though still existing.

PV performance in different geographies is evaluated; Tozeur (Tunisia), Seville (Spain,) Munich (Germany), Vilnius (Lithuania), and Oslo (Norway), applying the *SUPER PV best estimate* as described above for hypothetical utility scale PV facilities. Apart from location, the *Weighted Average Cost of Capital* (WACC) is the most important variable affecting the LCOE for solar PV [5, 6, 7]. The WACC depends on many factors such as country, market segment, and perception of risk, and hence the LCOE is calculated at varying WACC. Overall, the cost of finance for solar PV has been reduced over time in conjunction with the growing acceptance and recognition of solar power around the globe [6, 7]. It is reasonable to expect this development to continue.

The LCOE is calculated in real money at an assumed inflation rate of 2% and 0% corporate tax rate, with solar insolation data at optimum tilt angle from Solar GIS (Tozeur, Seville, Munich) and PVGIS and assumed performance ratio (PR) for *base case* shown in Table II. The PR will vary between different locations due to higher ambient temperatures in warmer climates, resulting in a reduced energy yield.

Table II: Solar insolation data and assumed PR *base case*

Location	Insolation kWh/(m ² day)	PR <i>base case</i> %
Tozeur	6.13	83
Seville	5.77	85
Munich	3.75	87
Vilnius	3.29	89
Oslo	3.15	89

The calculated LCOE is shown in Figure 8 as a function of the WACC. The figure illustrates clearly that local irradiation and the cost of finance are two crucial factors influencing the LCOE.

Figure 8: Calculated SUPER PV LCOE *best estimate*

The solar irradiation advantage for the southernmost locations vs the northern locations is comparable to a 6% change in WACC, i.e., the calculated LCOE for Norway at 3% WACC is close to the calculated LCOE for Tunisia at 9% WACC.

The calculated LCOE is compared with available spot price information for the relevant EU countries (Germany, Lithuania, and Spain) [8], Tunisia [9] and Norway [10], shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: SUPER PV *best estimate* LCOE at 3% and 7% WACC compared with spot market prices (network/grid, taxes and levies not included)

The SUPER PV *best estimate* LCOE is lower than the market price in every country except Norway even at a relatively high WACC of 7%, and for (southern) Norway the figure indicates that solar PV is on the verge of becoming competitive.

Long-term estimates from Statnett [10] indicate a power price range of 35-60€/MWh on the European continent towards 2030-40. For southern Norway an average price in the range of 35-40€/MWh is projected after 2030.

4 CONCLUSIONS

At this point the results from SUPER PV are overall promising. Key remaining activities are to extract field data at the SUPER PV demo-sites in Lithuania, Norway, Spain, Tunisia, and Morocco to ensure final validation of performance, and to prepare business models and -plans for market uptake after project end (October 2022).

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